

Title

Adoption of Social Work Technology in Africa: Possibilities and Realities

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Abstract

The introduction of new technologies has changed the face of social work practice and education around the world. African social work practitioners and education perceive the use of technology as a threat that might replace the usual traditional practice and there are very social work institutions and agencies utilizing technology in the provision of social services in the region. Therefore, the paper explores the possibilities and realities of social work technology in the African region. The paper presents the possibility of social work technology in the

African region with the advent of different technological applications in the region and can meet the needs of the hard-to-reach populations. A realistic social work technology in the African region needs to start from simple use of electronic social case management system to the level of online social services like (e-mental health services, podcast, online education, video-chat- interview sessions and electronic data management techniques) at all levels of ecological model of social work practice.

Key words

social work, technology, adoption, possibilities, realities and Africa

Introduction

The introduction of the Information Communication Technology (ICT) around the world has changed the face of human services and social work profession significantly. Social workers in the contemporary times provides services to their clients using different techniques like the use of telephone counselling, videoconferencing, self-guided web-based intervention services while utilizes the electronic social networks, mobile application, emails, text and host of other services in most developed countries like United State and other European region (Association of Social Work Boards, 2015; Mishna, Bogo, Root, Sawyer & Khoury-Kassabri, 2012). Social work technology around the world is gradually gaining recognition as its service area hovers around clinical practice, administration, advocacy and community organizing and research (CSWE, National Association of Social Workers technological standards, 2017). The 2017 NASW document on standards in technology in social work explained the use, benefits and limitation of the technology in the ecological systems (NASW, 2017). The NASW (2017) document emphasized the use of the information on the use of technology in social services at individual level, family and society at large. Detailed information about the content of the document is explained in the later part of this article.,

Background

Social Work practitioners in developed countries are gradually shifting focus towards the adoption of technology in teaching, intervention and development of policy for the vulnerable population (Ko & Rossen, 2017) but this has been able to translate that other professionals that utilizes technology in the provision of social services because it is critical in the improvement of lives of the disadvantaged population (Young, 2014). Compared to most African countries like South Africa and Nigeria, the adoption of technology is still at the infancy stage because of the low level of literacy of some social workers, poor motivation to use technology in social services, limited access to information technology and several other factors (Turner, 2016) Social work practice in the African region is been utilized as a curative or remedial approach to solving social problems from inception. In the African region, the effect of western technology has both blessings and curse because there is a slow progression in the adoption of appropriate indigenous scientific knowledge to address human needs as they depend solely on western technology (Lumum, 2013).

The main objective of the social work profession is the promotion of the wellbeing of individuals, families, promotion of social change, human relationship and liberation of people towards enhancing wellbeing (International Federation of Social Workers, 2018). Social workers educators like every other professional in disciplines often find it difficult to effectively perform their function without the advent of technology like the use of online teaching, infographics, etc. The indispensable use of technology in human society should prompt social work to pause and consider digital development in a rapidly changing society. Therefore, the thrust of this paper is to explore the adoption of technology in social work practice and

teaching while also examining the challenges (Pitfalls) and the reality of social work technology in the African region.

Social Work Technology in Africa: Adoption

The African region seems to be lagging in terms of the use of information technologies, although being the second largest continent among the least computerized nations of the world. Although, several international agreements support access to technology and improvement of technological capacity in the African continents (United Technology Innovation Lab, 2019).

Technology has contributed to social change across the African continent, it must not be forgotten that less than 11% of internet subscribers are from the African region and only 35.2% of the Africans use the internet (Internet Society, 2019). Moreover, the region often exhibits a digital divide with recent internet activities and infrastructural concentration in Africa continents like South Africa, Morocco, Egypt including smaller economies like Mauritius and Seychelles (World Economic Forum, 2019). The problem in the region is not lack of determination or the desire to meet-up with the rest of the world in terms of technological advancement. The problem is more related to the magnitude of development challenges in most developing countries where there is paucity of resources and delay in the effort to the eradication of poverty and achieve sustainable development. If this technology gap is not closed, most African countries will find it difficult to achieve the 2030 agenda of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the objective of leavening no one behind might not be achieved (Fekitamoeloa, 2018).

Africa is a continent with more than 50 countries and characterized by several factors which have a major influence on facilitating the genesis of the social

work profession (Lengwe-Katembula, 2011). The missionaries, support aids organization in the African region with support of the European government contributed significantly to the development of social work in the region (Global Social Service Workforce Alliance, 2017). In summary, social work in the African region is relatively young having introduced the profession in the 1960s, although, the Cairo School of Social Work, Egypt was the first school of social work in Africa and was established in 1937, the professional services and practice did not take effect until 1960s (Lengwe-Katembula, 2011). Most African countries that were colonized attained their independence in the 60s through rapid succession, although with several regional differences in terms of the dimension of social problems, economic growth, social development as well political engagement (Global Social Service Workforce Alliance, 2017). Today, there are several African countries with social work professions like Zimbabwe, South Africa, Zambia, Ethiopia, Swaziland, Nigeria, Uganda, Ghana, Kenya, Tanzania, Rwanda and Egypt training their social workers. The training of social workers in the region is majorly been performed by University and polytechnics. Social work practice is mostly integrated into government agencies, like hospitals, correctional services, police and defence department where major casework methods are mostly utilized by promoting the dignity for the vulnerable by supporting them to attain full potentials in the society (Global Social Service Workforce Alliance, 2017)

The uniformly developed ethical standards for technology in social work practice was developed by the Association of Social Work Boards, Council of Social Work Education and Clinical Social Work Association in partnership with the National Association of Social Workers (USA) in 2017 to serve as a guide on Ethical Application of Technology in Social Work Practice. But unfortunately, most African Social Work practitioners and educators do not have access to these documents for possible adoption and utilization in the region. However, the pioneers of social work in Africa in the late 19th and early 20 centuries could not have imagined that the professions of working tools in the 21st century will involve the provision of online social services, like social networking video counselling, email and cyber-therapy (NASW, ASWB & CSWE, 2017; Okoye, 2013).

The use of the digital and electronic device has unleashed several staggering of several ethical and risky provision of social services through this platform which also involves competence, privacy, confidentiality, conflict, informed consent, maintenance of dual relationship, boundaries, consultation, client referral, termination,

documentation and research evidence (East & Havard, 2015). The widespread use of technology in social work in the region is still controversial as some of the social workers are uncomfortable with the inclusion of technology into the profession (Parab, Palkar, Maurya & Balpande, 2017). In the clinical settings, social workers who provide distance counselling service might experience difficulty when maintaining clear boundaries when building their relationship with the client (Sawrikar, Lenette, McDonald, & Fowler, 2015).

In developed countries where technology is often utilized, Lee & Walsh, (2015) examined the use of mobile technology for meeting the needs of the underserved population through the use of mDad (Mobile Device Assisted Dad) a smartphone application to augment existing social work practices by providing fatherly-friendly services to help new father learn about engaging with their infants and mother. Social work technology has not grown to this in most developing African countries but it will surely serve its purpose of reaching the underserved communities. According to Chan (2016) that the internet might be very less important in the provision of social work services, the digital revolution has changed the social interaction system. This is because it provides options to deal with old human inequalities and also promotes social development in all understandings (López-Peláez & Díaz, 2015). Social Workers in Africa still have paucity of information about how the technology is opening new stage for the intervention of social workers (Chan & Holosko, 2016), for social work educators, technological use in teaching and research is also still developing as very few schools currently utilize technology in social work education (Goldkind, 2014) for institutions that use it, it is mostly through distance online social work education. Also, the application of technology in social work training has grown significantly and has continuously shaped the delivery of social work education when effectively and creatively used, it can create new methods in social work training in schools in developing countries like Africa.

Although, social work educators are aware of the potential impact of using technology in training future social work professionals can obtain and assess relevant information that is evidence-based during their practice (Brady, et al, 2016), because they mostly rely on social network and social media use to inform practice as well as pedagogical training of students. Adaptation of technology in social work in Africa still has slow penetration because of the paucity of resources, infrastructural facilities, erratic power supply (Ebingbo & Okoye, 2015), computer literacy is still low among social workers, lack of awareness among the social workers in the use of technology is very low (Misha, Fantus & Mdnroy, 2017; Haliso, 2011). Social work

technology in the region is lagging-behind due to several factors resulting from limited resources, ethico-legal consideration, lack of training and historical reliance on face-to-face social interaction among social workers and educators. Social work educators often report inadequate instructive guidelines to provide evidence-based standard social work training through the use of technology (Wolf & Goldkind 2016; Reamer, 2015).

Possibilities of Social Work technology in Africa

Social Work technology in Africa is very possible when there are appropriate structures in place. Although a broad spectrum of social work professionals strives to promote face-to-face interaction with their client, but the use of technology in managing their client's data and time because the use of technology in practice has both advantages and challenges because it serves the purpose of keeping meticulous records, sharing important information around social services agencies in the region. The possibilities of social work technology in Africa also comes with challenges like information security, reliability and accessibility (Turner, 2016).

The importance of the social work profession remains committed to the improvement of the wellbeing of individuals and families. This makes the profession to be actively committed to the use of technology in one of the twelve Social Work Grand Challenge on Harnessing Technology for Social Good, the Grand Challenge calls for the development of new innovative ways for the profession to integrate technology in the fulfilment of vision and mission for the benefit of society and emerging social work professionals (Berzin, et al 2016). Furthermore, the Grand challenge also recommended expansion of internet connectivity for underserved households because everyday life is increasingly requiring the use of the internet to do several things like searching for an apartment, learning about job openings, submitting an employment or university application, health information and obtaining government benefits are mostly done through the online platform (Berzin, et al 2016; Turner, 2016). These recommendations are very possible in the African Social Work Practice and Education (Turner, 2016) when government and institutions invest in technology for social good it improves easy access to welfare services. Although access to internet connectivity in most African countries is still very low because the region has been experiencing limited and expensive fixed broadband internet connectivity for a long time (Fekitamoeloa, 2018), several countries in the region are covered by 3G internet services, which enables most African citizens to have access to a commerce site, digital entertainment, educational

content and telehealth technological services (Kimura, et al, 2010), the projection is, internet technology is expected to add-up with more than 300 billion dollars to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the African Continent by 2025 (Manyika, et al 2013).

Furthermore, recommendation two from the Grand Challenge indicates unlocking government data to drive solutions to social problems. This recommendation encourages numerous agencies at all levels to generate administrative records for program improvement and policy effectiveness (Berzin, et al 2015). In the African region, developing successful information management, it will require collaborative efforts including social workers who have been categorized as one of the frontline workers (Reardon, 2010). We live in an ever-growing digital society where data management is so much important and remain untapped for social work practice, policy formulation and social action (Grogan-Kaylor & Dunkle, 2014). Hence, governments of the African might find it extremely difficult to implement an intervention for the vulnerable in society without the availability of data. The provision of web-based information management for service providers and human service workers in developing countries has a positive impact on productivity and outcome on social intervention (George, et al, 2015).

Most African social service sectors do not have electronic social casework management system but for the institution that has, it is mostly recorded in an excel sheet (Oyinlola, 2016), most possible it is incorporated in the National Health information management system like Nigeria (Oyinlola, 2016). Data management is very important in the provision of social services and serves as a tool to engage the government of the African region. Another indication for a possible Social Work Technology in Africa is the fact that Schools of Social Work in other countries like the USA and other European countries have been very fortunate to experience the impact of the use of technology most especially in the delivery of social work curriculum (Sage, Hitchcock & Smith, 2019). Only a few schools offer online social work programmes for individuals residing in hard-to-reach communities for years in the West African region (Canavera, Akesson, Landis, Armstrong & Meyer, 2019). In developed countries where online courses are delivered through videoconference, Facebook or through has been found to be very effective to learning (Sage et al, 2019) while some countries in the African region like South Africa and Botswana are providing Open and Distance learning in social work (Chikadzi & Pretorius, 2014; Cooner, 2014).

In the 21st century, there had been unprecedented growth in virtual learning in most developed

countries as most social work schools around the world rapidly designing and implementing unique platforms to provide an asynchronous and synchronous social work education through (Self-paced, online, web-based content, live sessions using the video streaming capabilities (Wernet, et al 2000). The importance of considering online social work education is to assist the student who is long-distance commuters and also students with a disability, where the course educator can utilize a course management system like (Sakai, Blackboard and Moodle) for ensuring students are managed virtually in all aspect of the course (Goldkind & Wolf, 2015). The possibility of technology in social work education in Africa will change the face of administration and academic function in most colleges and universities in the region as students will be able to accomplish several tasks using several networks which saves the institution a lot of time and money (Sawrikar, Lenette, McDonald, & Fowler, 2015).

Realities of Social Work technology in Africa

Traditional/Indigenous social workers do not see Social Work Technology in Africa as a reality or possibility because the continent is being overshadowed by cultural heritage, it is not considered as a novel and the fear that it might take over human face-to-face human interaction over the next decades (for example electronic counselling, social network site, emails, mobile applications and automated tutorials lecturers are being feared). It is important to state that technology is advancing and African social workers should rise to the challenge of developing a tech sense in all areas of practice or education (Singer and Sage, 2016). Social Work Technology is real, it has its uses, benefits and limitations in the area of micro, mezzo and macro practice, community organizing and policy formulation. Social Work services today involve several digital and electronic options which also include several numbers of working tools for delivery of social services to clients (Blanco 2016). Although the development and use of technology in social services emanated from clinical practice which involves the use of the computer (online chats and email) including other electronic means like smartphones, video technology to provide services to clients, communicate with clients and also the management of confidential case records (Lomax & Nix, 2015; Young, 2012).

The internet has several features of online mental health services which are aimed at helping individuals who struggle with depression, addiction, marital and relationship conflict, anxiety, grief and other mental health conditions including behavioural challenges (Chandra, 2016; Singer & Sage, 2016). These services can happen in the

African where there is access to internet facilities which enable such individuals can search to locate a medical social worker who offers counselling services through online chat platform, this can offer anonymous writing experience, with the benefit of immediate response from the online social worker (Wodarski & Frimpong, 2013).

There are few pieces of literature in the Africa region focusing on the use of technology in social work practice especially online mental health. Empirical studies have not been able to find a difference in outcomes between synchronous (e.g live webcam) and asynchronous (e.g email) online therapy, some online environment may be most appropriate for some certain mental health problem like Virtual reality (VR for treating Post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) or phobia, text-based reminders for medication compliance) (Chan, 2016; Pallavicini et al, 2013). A comparative analysis of the use of face-to-face and online service has consistently reported positive mental health outcome (Martinez-Brawley, 2016; Dowling & Rickwood, 2013; Gillingham, 2016; Richards & Viganó, 2013) in several other cases it is better than face-to-face therapy session (Groshong, & Phillips, 2015). This implies that for social work practice and education to be sustainable, suitable and structured, technology has to be incorporated into practice and education of social work. Although there are limitations to online mental health services as existing evidence reported that online therapies have received some little setbacks from older persons and older social workers because they are less likely to trust the online mental health services (Dowling & Rickwood, 2013), though it might provide some level of online support it is more suitable for individuals who grew up in the era of ICT than individuals who did not (Singer & Sage, 2016). Since online mental health services are still recent, the long-term effect has not been effectively established (So, et al, 2013).

In the area of community organization and development, the vulnerable and marginalized groups were negatively affected by the advent of technology (Berzin, Singer & Chan, 2015). In the African region where fewer populations have online access (Purcell, et al, 2012), knowing fully well that access to internet connectivity has educational advantages in terms of information access, applying for jobs and also enhance computer skills (Araque, et al 2013) among communities experiencing problems such as bullying, sex trafficking. Although lack of access to technology has become a social problem for some communities in the African region which makes the practice of social work technology seemly become a dream that might not work in the continent. Towards making social work technology among communities in Africa a reality, organizing efforts must acknowledge and address the digital

divide towards preventing the exclusion of very important groups that would benefit from participation in advocacy efforts.

ICT in the 21st century has made 24/7 access to the internet through the smartphone and tablet has built a virtual community without an offline counterpart, hence social workers working in the community setting have negotiated the paradox engaging the marginalize and disenfranchise group towards ameliorating social problems. Social workers in this century need to organize both physical and virtual communities (Lopez-Pelaez, 2015). There are two primary categories technologies social workers can use when navigating the community 1. Tools to mediate communication and deliver messages like emails, listserve, social networks like (Facebook, twitter etc) and blogs. 2. Tools for data collection and visualization such as social case management, GIS and automated subscription-based alert system (Marzouki & Qullier, 2012). According to Pillay & Maharaj, (2014) also reported a positive impact of social media and mobile communication among civil servants in South Africa using Web 2.0. However, among users, there is a low level of knowledge of the importance of social media usage among the civil society organization in the country. Other technology been used for community development and advocacy is the Geographic Information System (GIS) which is used in analyzing regions, zip codes, cities and countries (Felke, 2006; Teixeira, 2018). The GIS can also be used by advocacy groups to analyse campaign demographics towards improving voter participation when adopted in the Africa region (Schoepfer, 2014).

Additionally, policy issues around social work technology in Africa are dependent on agency function and might inform the social worker's decision to participate in online forums. Although several social work agencies do not have specific social media policy in terms of the way they communicate on the social work, representing their organization through the social media platform and ensuring positive online identity (Ballantyne, Wong, & Morgan, 2017). Social Work practitioners and educators should understand that they represent their employer and permanence of online posting (Kimball & Kim, 2013) also online activities are monitored among social workers employed by the government (Schoepfer, 2014). Social workers are excellent policy developers, the employer could ask them to draft e-therapy or social media focusing on justification, the prohibition in social media use, consequences of policy violation and consider the impact the positive and negative impact of social media use on clients (Reamer, 2015). There must be emerging ethical standards regarding social worker's use of technology which are embedded in the adopted model regulatory laws promulgated

American Social Work Board (ASWB) and was jointly developed by NASW, ASWB, CSWE and CSWA highlighted several common core concepts and themes: involving the provision of information to the public, designing of information, managing, storing and gathering of information; building a collegial relationship, educating students and practitioners (NASW, 2017). Social work technology during policy formulation pave ways for thinking about boundaries in a professional relationship while it is built to prevent marginalization exploitation among the most vulnerable population in the society (British Association of Social Workers, 2012). Social Work roles may be shifted to access more available information for practitioners towards becoming aggregator and ensuring legitimate information is sources to the client (Chan & Holosko, 2016)

Social Work technology in Africa should face the reality of the changing dynamics in the technology world because it is transformational in connecting, creating access, new opportunities to rethinking social work practice and education. Social work practitioners and education should remain alert to drive and also embrace the new movement as the world becomes reliant on technology, leveraging in digital advances for social good. In a bid to make this a reality in the African continents, social services would be made available to individuals who have traditionally been socially excluded as a result of location, immobility, transportation and barriers which are enhanced by integrated ICT.

Recommendations

Technology enabled social work practice as continued to change the face of the practice setting as well as reduction of workloads. It is therefore recommended there is need for the development of facilities in the area of technology in social work education to better prepare social workers to participate in a wide range of policy initiatives to support activities that address the disparities hovering around social, economic and political participation in the African region. In a bid to ensure African social work practice and education, there is a need to uphold the ethical standards and values in social work through the use of technology. There is a need for social workers to be literate and competent in the use of technology.

Conclusion

Despite the increasing growth and development of technologies in the African region, several marginalized and vulnerable groups still do not have access to technologies or internet facilities. The signs that technology might takeover social work interventions around the work is prevalent each day. It can be concluded that Social Work Technology in

Africa can be adopted, made possible and realistic in the face of global technological advancement. Social work practice and education in Africa has not adequately adopted the use of technology in the discharge of their duties at all levels of social work profession. Social work profession still experiences difficulties using the online platforms and the African social work practitioners have not sufficiently used digitalization thus far. The reality is, the rapidly growing technology in Africa, social workers cannot resist technology. In the coming

decades, there are possibilities that social work services will be entirely technology-based, other groups might have minimal integration with technology. The youth of today will become tomorrow's consumers, and they see very little difference between the identity between online and offline platforms. Social workers will have to demonstrate their knowledge and skills with the use of technology in the provision of treatment in any environment they work.

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